

Walking Hundreds of Miles under the Cloud of COVID-19

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A lifeless but an invisible novel corona virus has shattered the rhythm of daily life in our interconnected global village. The threat of this invisible has become invincible due to lack of vaccine to prevent COVID-19. Consequently, an enforced and effective social distancing at the sphere of social life, and washing one's hands regularly for 20 seconds with soap-water or alcohol-based hand rub at the personal level seem to be the current mode of preventing the spread of novel corona virus, and protecting oneself. This has led many governments around the globe opt for national or regional lockdowns for varying periods of time. The Indian government, following the practice prevalent at the present international scenario enforced a nationwide three-week-long lockdown on 25 March 2020.

A Bold Step, But ...

The declaration of national lockdown—a bold step in the right direction—to contain the spread of coronavirus pandemic, that has devastated more than 230 countries around the globe, has led unfortunately to an unprecedented exodus of hundreds of thousands of migrant workers from various cities and towns in India. On the one hand, it made clear that the economic activities related to unorganized sectors depend on movement and migration, but on the other, it brought to the fore the vulnerability of thousands of millions of migrant workers in India.

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The Plight of the Migrant Workers

In the wake of the government's twenty-one days national lockdown, the migrant workers—women, men and children—had no option but to set out on foot from cities, their temporary worksites, for their “homes” in villages thousands of miles away. They were walking down on national and state highways in the past week

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hungry and thirsty, tired and exhausted, blisters on their feet and yet their young ones on their shoulders and bags perched on their heads. Some of them were forcefully doused with disinfectant, upon crossing the state borders. More than two scores of people died on their way and a couple of them were burnt in the forest fires on the border between states.

Ramachandra Guha, an eminent historian of India, lamented at the flight of the migrant workers, “Those who build our cities, houses, hospitals, hotels, multiplexes and do lots of things that make our lives in middle class urban India comfortable are neither an administrative nor societal priority”. They were going home, which they left in search of a better life, in hundreds and thousands with tormenting hearts about their bleak future ahead of them. They were walking on the roads towards their distant homes, because they were left without daily wages, food, temporary shelters and security in their worksites, the big cities. They were fleeing away, in a time of unprecedented crisis and uncertainty caused by an inexplicable fear of the novel corona virus—fear of getting infected or spreading the infection, anxiety and concerns about their families thousands of miles away—from their economic

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insecurity and social anonymity in the cities in search of their original nests that provided an emotional and scanty economic security.

United Nations High Commissioner for Human Rights, Michelle Bachelet, said on 02 April, that the plight of the millions of internal migrants in the wake of the ill-planned national lockdown imposed to contain COVID-19 outbreak in India, should not “exacerbate existing inequalities and vulnerabilities”. While appreciating the subsequent measures taken by the ruling regimes, she was categorical in asserting that “pervasive changes still remain to reach out to the most vulnerable sectors” of Indian society.

As per the Centre’s report submitted to the Supreme Court of India towards the fall of March 2020, there are more than 4.14 crores migrants in different states, but the actual number will be much higher. The millions of migrant workers were the life-line of the unorganized sector, which keeps the Indian economy buzzing. Their numbers have been growing in the last decades but their lives remain precarious infected with myriad of miseries. They have no social security, no contracts and other benefits in their worksites. Their exodus from the big cities driven by the fear of the novel corona virus “has made them a lot more visible in the national discourse”. Thanks to the state governments who under the directive from the Centre have quarantined the migrant workers in make-shift shelters for two weeks in order to prevent the movement of people across state borders and curb the spread of the new virus and prevent transmission in the villages far-off from the international and national airports.

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Ramachandra Guha

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Lack of Political Voice and Agency

The national lockdown triggered by the fear of new corona virus has made bare the despair and abject powerlessness of the migrant workers, and the best kept secret, “policy and data gaps on migrant workers”. Although they have been part of the Indian cityscape for decades now, their near “invisibility in official statistics” kept them and their utter poverty and powerlessness away from the decision-making tables at the national and state levels. The migrant workers remain invisible to political and administrative structures because they are not registered voters in the cities. They remain invisible in their own constituencies also because they are thousands of miles away from there. Divya Varma and Divya Ravindranath, renowned migration scholars, pointed it out in one of their articles of 2019, “Devoid of voting rights in the urban destinations that they [migrants] help build with their labour, their lives are stripped of any form of political voice or agency.”

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The migrant workers in unorganized sectors due to their informal status in the places of their labour could not avail the benefits provided under the public welfare policies. Their poverty and vulnerability mantle those who hire them with a culture of impunity, a culture that has no space for any obligation towards them, except a low wage. The Indian Health Ministry’s recent statement stated that the migrants are “the most marginalized section of the society who are dependent on daily wages for their living, and in times of such distress need sympathy and understanding of the society”. The unprecedented exodus of millions of migrant workers triggered

by the national lockdown to contain COVID-19, gives us a clarion call that their human dignity is sacred; their rights and privileges have not only to be respected in the texture of everyday life but must be constitutionally protected, and justice must be seen realized and experiential in their fragile lives away from their homes.

Conclusion: Plea for New Forms of Hospitality, Fraternity and Solidarity

Certainly, there will be and should be celebrations as the corona virus pandemic recedes in the coming months, but the disturbing images of millions of migrants workers, who were not scared to walking thousands of miles on our roads, should orient us towards the task ahead, as John Gray, a political philosopher, articulated, “to build economies and societies that are more durable, and more humanly habitable, than those that were exposed to the anarchy of the global market”. While speaking of the link between catastrophe and faith, Heribert Butterfield in his book, *Christianity and History* (1949) said: “the pandemic has humbled the country and opened millions of eyes to this risky universe once more.” The corona virus pandemic calls us to create space for, as Pope Francis said, “new forms of hospitality, fraternity and solidarity” (*Urbi et Orbi* on 27 March 2020).

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